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Echoes of Social Change: Audience Awareness in Contemporary Nigerian Poetry

Jude Zealous ADEGOKE,
Lecturer,
Department of English and Literary Studies,
Prince Abubakar Audu University,
Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria.

***Abstract:** For reasons bordering on its socially committed disposition, contemporary Nigerian poetry often attempts to reach a broad and general audience that is largely semi-literate. Poets, whose ideology aligns with this vision, therefore use comprehensible, shared, and simple language to access such an audience. This focus on accessibility often comes at the expense of artistic quality unless the two are judiciously balanced. This work investigates how contemporary Nigerian poets balance artistic complexity and popular audience appeal to convey messages and effect social change. The study aims to discover the ways in which such poets make poetry more popular without making concessions on artistic value. The study draws on Realism as a theoretical framework, while adopting qualitative research methodology. Through the content analysis of the selected poems, the study discovers that these poets are greatly aware of their audience, and they employ straightforward language, familiar imagery and symbolism their poetry to connect with the masses. In this manner, contemporary Nigerian poets are able to reach more and general readers, which mean that they are interested in conveying the Nigerian masses' socio-political problems. This, however, does not diminish the literary value of their poetry, for it bristles with literary devices that set it apart from other forms of literature. This simplicity of style itself can effect social change by connecting with the masses and spurring them to action.*

Keywords: Audience awareness, contemporary Nigerian poetry, Simplicity, The masses, Social change

Introduction

Contemporary Nigerian poets are always mindful of their audience, cognisant of their key role in effective transmission, especially in their quest for the desired social reform. Writers associated with this school of thought such as Ezenwa Ohaeto, Peter Onwudinjo, Tanure Ojaide, and Niyi Osundare emphasise the accessibility of their poetry. They postulate that the simpler the poetry, the more potent it becomes in its quest to mobilise the teeming masses to effect social change, particularly because the masses, as agents of change, can only relate to a simple poetic language. This research examines how Nigerian contemporary poetry achieves the audience-awareness paradigm in pursuing social transformation with artistic integrity preserved.

Critiques of the Audience-Awareness Paradigm in Nigerian Poetry

Those who defend audience consciousness in Nigerian poetry might assert that in the age of information overload and low attention span, an otherwise relatively accessible style of poetry and tradition would be a tactical choice to reach a wider audience and deliver messages of social transformation effectively. Therefore, an inaccessible poetic style characterised by elegant linguistic construction and almost unfamiliar imagery and symbolism would defeat the ultimate essence of his communication to broader and diverse audiences. In this vein, exponents of the audience-conscious school of thought recommend that the language of any audience-conscious poetry should be disambiguated, categorically straightforward, and commonplace –almost without any embellishment. This paradigm is evident in the poetry of the Alter-Natives, prompting Suede Agema to declare that modern African poets, especially the generation after the first, display a high level of social commitment, averring that “their

commitment is much that even their words and language used in writing bear the trademark of dedication.”In his substantiation of this proposition, Aderemi Bamikunle remarks that contemporary African poetry is socially engaged in favour of the disadvantaged; hence,

...it is to avoid all forms of elitism in language use by being accessible. As a corollary, his subjects will be down-to-earth as he avoids such metaphysical flights of the imagination of the elitist poetry of his predecessors. (35)

The elitism present in the poetry of the preceding generation, which seemingly undervalued audience engagement and linguistic simplicity, triggered calls and protests for a return to genuine African cultural elements, such as traditional imagery, songs of sorrow, and spiritual invocations, along with a reconnection of modern poetry with oral traditions, referred to as the Alter-Native Tradition. This new breed of poets, writing in the new poetic tradition, aimed to demystify African poetry. They did this by simplifying its language and emphasising the use of traditional imagery and oral traditions, which resonate deeply with a vast majority of Africans. In his critical opinion on the representative figure of the new generation, and by extension, the generality of the group, Abdu Saleh posits:

Osundare’s poetic style marks him as a representative voice of the group. Through a studied critique and reworking of the language of their predecessors, Osundare leads the group in their tacit task of liberating and demystifying the business of poetry to many readers. As language and language use lie in the essence of poetry, African poetry can only gain its distinctive voice quality by the degree to which its language—African or borrowed European— is shaped and reflected in the local African experience. (49)

Obi Maduakor, a prominent figure in Nigerian poetry, attributes the origins of this audience-awareness trend to the

Nigerian civil war of the late 1970s. He suggests that Nigerian poetry's evolving style and themes began to reflect the country's changing socio-political and economic circumstances. In his words, "a new attitude in language, the war revolutionised the attitude to the language of Nigerian poetry imbued it with new energy, a new direction, and a new urgency" (49).

The drive to connect with broader and diverse audiences is a strong motivation for incorporating pidgin as a means of communication in contemporary African poetry. Despite Pidgin's association with the low social group and its pejorative connotations, it emerges as the language of dedication to the suffering masses. Given its accessibility to both literate and semi-literate Nigerians, poetry expressed in pidgin has the potential to connect with a vast majority of the population, encouraging them to engage with poetry for their enjoyment. This appeal transcends the borders of Nigeria, as non-Nigerians can also comprehend the essence of such pieces. According to Peter Onwudinjo:

Pidgin is the language of West African urban cities where millions of Nigerians from various linguistic backgrounds dwell and eke out a marginal living. Pidgin is the highway to the Nigerian urban poor audiences, most of whom do not read and write. Pidgin poetry yields its meaning without undue tasking of the intellectual resources of the reader. ...Because Pidgin is so powerful, and reaches a wider local audience. (vii)

Similarly, Ikechukwu Emmanuel Asikaposits that, "With the use of the Pidgin language, our poets create poetry very familiar to the woman in the market, a palm-wine tapper on a tree, a fisherman in a boat and a weary tout smoking under the mango tree on a hot dizzy day" (103). Pidgin speaks to the people and speaks for them, too, since poets write for the people and their conditions(96). Though modern poetry has incorporated pidgin as a communication medium, it remains aesthetically captivating, especially as evident in the figurative use of language. The

contemporary poet can reach a broader audience through this singular medium.

Nevertheless, Donatus Nwoga's stance challenges the prevailing notion that Nigerian poetry should be produced in a most simplified and easily understandable diction. Instead, he holds a positive view of the complex poetry produced by Euro-Modernist African poets, judging that while such poetry may not yield its meanings easily to the audience, an intellectual engagement with it would create the necessary outcomes. He declares thus:

It would be naïve, however, to think that because the poems (of the Euro-modernist poets) are written by fellow Africans, they should be understood, appreciated and enjoyed immediately and without any effort by the African readers. No writing of any value can yield its beauties so easily to any reader. We know, for example, that the English have been writing books upon books to help themselves understand their own poets. We must be ready to work for our enjoyment and our mental and emotional development. (iii)

Nwoga's revisionist position challenges the prevailing attitude that Nigerian poets must prefer simplicity in their poetry, especially given the harsh realities of the modern age and the demands of social transformation. Nwoga argues against the assumption that African readers should readily comprehend, appreciate, and enjoy poems by fellow Africans, and especially those poems that have been influenced by Euro-modernist traditions.

A striking aspect of Nwoga's criticism is his rejection of the proposal that poetry, regardless of its origin, should be immediately accessible to readers. His contention is that good writing requires effort and engagement on the part of the reader and cites English readers who have had to labour at appreciating

their own poets. It challenges the notion of simplifying poetry for easy consumption, arguing rather that complexity and depth have to be embraced, even if it requires intellectual and emotional labour on the reader's part. It has to be noted here, however, that while Nwoga's stance encourages the intellectual and emotional labour required in the closer appreciation of poetry, it need not necessarily discount the imperative to open up literature to the reader. The challenge is to balance artistic integrity and appeal to a heterogeneous readership. This research uses selected poems to examine how contemporary Nigerian poetry captures the paradigm of audience awareness in its quest for social change while maintaining artistic integrity.

Realism: A Theoretical Justification

This research uses Realism as the theoretical framework for examining audience awareness in selected contemporary Nigerian poems that engage in social change themes. Realism as a literary tendency gives precedence to the truthful representation of everyday life and social facts, often foregrounding the struggles of ordinary people in recognisable socio-political situations (Watt 11).

Nigerian poetry extracts its material from concrete realities. This makes Realism a significant critical framework through which critics can read poets' handling of pressing issues. Realism anatomises such social ills as poverty, political instability, social injustice, corruption, resistance, etc, especially as they pertain to audience consciousness and response. The poems under study employ minimalist language, concrete imagery, familiar symbols, as well as down-to-earth subject matter to connect with readers. This has the tendency to foster critical thinking and socio-political consciousness among the audience, often considered the agents of social change.

Analysing the Audience Awareness Paradigm in Selected Poems

Many contemporary Nigerian poets, including G'ebinyo Ogbowei, demonstrate their sensitivity to their audience through "their use of language" (Anasiusu 148) in their works. For example, in the first section of his poem, "marsh boy," Ogbowei poetically shows an acute awareness of his audience evident in the manner in which he conveys complex social issues through simple language. Through the vivid imagery of being "locked in the prison of poverty" and "denied the right to rise" (21), the poet connects with a wider audience. Hence, he draws attention to the struggles faced by marginalised individuals in society. In addition, the poet employs words such as "creeks with crushed dreams" and "ponds with decaying hope" (21) so as to evoke empathy and understanding, hence making his message clear to all. This line captivates the minds of the audience and forces them to realize the need for rectifying social imbalances. The poem's call for opportunity and dignity amid exploitation and betrayal awakens the conscience of the audience, giving a moral compass to the poet's fight for social revolution. The poet relays:

i sing of ponds with decaying hope
i sing of rivers the cargo ship and
supertankers sail on
i sing of swamps sold to swindlers and
rustlers
i sing of swamps demanding dignity
and opportunity (21)

While "marsh boy" reaches a broader audience with plain diction, it creatively employs other examples of figurative diction to fill the poem's meaning. Poverty is likened to a prison and those on the outskirts to a marsh boy. This reflects feelings of confinement and domination on those living in poverty. The poet uses relatable symbolism, such as "swamps demanding dignity/and opportunity" to elicit a deep emotional response from the reader.

This poetic lines paint a vivid image of the downtrodden, whose existence has been suppressed by “swindlers and rusters” in their own home. Also, personification admirably lends voice to the swamps in the quest for social justice by "demanding dignity and opportunity" (21). These literary devices serve to heighten the poem's portrayal of poverty and marginalisation and amplify its message in terms of potency and poignancy.

Responding to the complexity of poetic forms in Nigerian literature, Osundare deeply queries, “Are we supposed to read it or toss it back to the shelves in endless desperation?” (Cited in Ogunyemi 249). He argues that socially conscious poetry should resonate with the suffering masses, bringing attention to their plight and inspiring them to confront the institutions responsible for their condition. For him, this will ultimately lead to a social revolution. In his collection *Songs of the Marketplace*, Osundare redefines poetry as “a life spring/which gathers timbre/the more throats it plucks/harbingers of action /the more minds it stirs” (1). The poet’s fundamental rejection of the previous concept of exclusive and obscure Nigerian poetry redefines the framework of Nigerian poetry. This act elucidates its essence, dimensions, and preferred medium while emphasising its accessibility to its intended audience. To illustrate this shift in perspective, Osundare, in the poem “Poetry Is,” includes the previously marginalised audience by stating that: ‘Poetry is/No oracles kernel/For sole philosopher’s stone/Poetry/Is/Man/Meaning/To/Man’ (1-2). This simplicity demonstrates the poet’s belief that “poetry must speak directly to and on behalf of the masses” (Adegoke and John 32).

In plain and eloquent prose, Osundare's "Forest Echoes" speaks to the grim realities of societal decline, moral decay, unseen intrigues, and fading joy in human existence. He identifies contemporary deficiencies and impermanence with nature, particularly the fast-decreasing trees and forests, and blames all variations on humanity's anthropocentric approach to nature. Worried about the trees, the poet explores the forest, where he encounters a scene of ravaged habitats resulting from deliberate

destruction by humans. Osundare conveys his dismay at the unhealthy transformation of once-vibrant forests, and laments in straightforward terms:

A forest of million trees, this
a forest of milling trees,
wounded, though by time's axe
and the greedy edges of Agbegilodo'smatchet. (5)

The proponents of this school, the audience-conscious Nigerian poets, are particularly captivating due to their "unapologetic and assertive use of African myths, folklore, proverbs, and speech patterns derived from their oral literary traditions" (Shija 254), along with their incorporation of familiar idioms and imagery. This affinity with local audiences further strengthens their connection with the cultural fabric.

Ojaide, known for his audience-awareness temperament, vehemently criticises complex poetic styles, advocating instead syntactic minimalism. He firmly believes that such a style allows the masses to comprehend the semantic implications of symbols, images, and the poet's message. Ojaide eschews esoteric and elitist language to contend that poetry in its simplest form is easily accessible to all literate members of Nigerian society, transcending stratification. In his poem "Labyrinths of the Delta," Ojaide unequivocally demonstrates his commitment to minimalism:

We took off without a thought of where we were going...
And paths opened for our anxious feet
It was not for fun men and women split from bed...
We rushed into the vast night
Living not in our homes
But caravaned in hope. (23)

The above excerpt unearths Ojaide's narrative, which uses "simple and direct language, telling the story of people under siege" (Olafioye 10). It appeals to local and foreign audiences and requires no interpreter for comprehension.

Linguistic accessibility is the hallmark of audience-engaged poetry, as it strives to provide solace for the marginalised in society. This principle is again exemplified in Osundare's poem "Advice," where he states:

To yourself
Friend, be true
You farm a hundred yams
And you tell us it is two hundred
Alright
After eating a hundred yams
You will eat a hundred lies.

The poem "Advice" reflects the nature of linguistically accessible poetry in that it does not require an interpreter to deconstruct its message for the average reader. The poem's observation against deceit, especially against politicians lying, is obvious and plain. Osundare attacks society by means of direct but metaphorical language and imagery, and individuals of every background are capable of relating to and interpreting the message. This accessibility is essential to the power of the poem because it causes its themes to resonate far and wide, going far beyond literary discourse and calling out and addressing societal injustices and norms.

Similarly, in "A Villager's Protest," Osundare again demonstrates himself adept at social commentary via everyday language and imagery. The poet's keen awareness of his audience is the most striking aspect of this poem. Here, Osundare employs familiar diction and imagery in his attempt to effectively expose the deceptive promises made by politicians during electioneering. The politician's voice is heard thus:

We'll build schools
We'll build hospitals...
We'll give the farmer

The best for his sweat
And make poverty
A thing of the past. (47)

Osundare's portrayal is unequivocal in revealing the hollowness of these assurances, as he exposes the truth behind the facade of electoral promises. The poet reveals that after securing electoral victory, the politicians transform into tyrants and oppressors of the masses, who voted them into power, betraying every campaign promise. Consequently, they indulge in immoral lifestyles, including promiscuity, extravagant spending, and reckless diversion their constituency allowances for personal and frivolous needs. They evolve into new figures; only their cars and not their faces become visible on the streets, symbolising their presence as they "thunder through the streets/and/our dust-laden mats announce the departure of the man of power"(48).Through the employment of metaphoric yet plain terms, he reveals the gap between political rhetoric and reality as well as the exploitative character of political elections in order to gain votes. This conscious effort to appeal to the readers makes the poem stronger in effect, with the potentiality of being read and comprehended by common people in general.

Similarly, Idris Amali's "Fear" begins with a display of courage, where the poet persona protests against military dictatorship and expresses a commitment to fighting for a just society without succumbing to fear He recounts experiences of witnessing horror and asserts his fortitude against military brutality, even in the face of sophisticated, heavy-duty guns:

I have sat with the seers
witches and the brave
at the peak of days and crack of nights
in the turbulent womb of groves
washed hands in cold and hot blood to dine.
Why should I fear and tremble

.....

Why should I tremble at your masked evil
that bakes the young to feed?
Why should I fear tomorrow
And these filthy cannons?

The above declaration reveals the poet's refusal to compromise or conceal the atrocities perpetrated by the ruling classes, opting for acerbic expression over a mild articulation of pent-up emotions. The revelations of the tyrants' deeds are vividly portrayed through repetitions and rhetorical questions, emphasising the poet's unwavering resolve in his protest endeavours. Personification and oxymorons, such as "turbulent womb of groves" and "cold and hot blood to dine," respectively, are deployed by the poet to enhance the portrayal of his firsthand experiences with absolute horror. Rather than being deterred by these distressing circumstances, they fuel the protest poet's courage and determination to expose the antisocial practices of the tyrants.

In a similar vein, Amali's poem, "The rain has not come," depicts the pathetic situation in which the poet and his people find themselves. Rain is a metaphor for good things, which can soothe people's pain, renew their hopes, and help their dreams materialise. However, those who seized the reins of government prevent 'the rain' from falling, causing us to "wallow/In the desert of distress." The poet uses the abhorrent image of flies as a metaphor for the dictators who dash the masses' hopes. He tells us that:

The rain has not come
As swarms of flies besiege
Our oases of hopes
Charred into cracks of distress.

He proceeds to depict the tyrants as 'brutes' and 'leeches.' He recognises the fact that they manipulated their way to their present positions. They are double-dealers, hence: "Parade as members/Of Anti-desert and flood committees. Having thought

deeply about the absence of ‘the rain,’ he realises there cannot be a balance where a small fraction of society is so powerful and could kill dreams. He uses reeds as a metaphor for the incestuous group, who live in luxury while others pass through hard times. Generally, reeds grow in marshes and other wetlands, so even without rain, they still blossom. At this point, the poet uses oxymorons to a specific effect as he tells us about reeds found in marshlands and the desert— an area of land with no permanent bodies of water and hardly any rainfall. This imagery presents us with two extremes: poverty and wealth. It highlights the structural imbalance that defines our society, where tyrants rule. He states thus:

But how could there have been rains
When our chase has become a race
To grip our silhouette
Cast against melting mountain of dreams
Where soldier ants
Blossom into baobab size
As only select reeds
Are nurtured in our desert of hostile faces
For the cannibal drum and dance.

In their attempts to reach broader and more diverse audiences, contemporary Nigerian poets deploy pidgin as a medium of poetic expression, thereby solidifying its status as a language capable of supporting literary endeavours. Ohaeto firmly observes that “it is clearly this capability of Pidgin to sustain works of literature – since it is a language that bridges orality, a language that absorbs several cultural elements as it communicates– which has made it yield creative possibilities for the Nigerian poet” (25). For instance, Ezenwa Ohaeto writes most of his poetry in Pidgin, capturing the attention of a broader audience because of his consciousness. He tells us in the poem “I Wan Bi President”:

I never see president hungry
I never see president thirsty
President no go worry for road

Police no go stop am for checking
President no go worry for house
Na government cook dey prepare food
Na government dry cleaner dey wash cloth
Na government driver dey drive motor
Na him make I wan bi president.(57)

The poet employs a lucid vocabulary to expose our political leaders' sybaritic, despotic, and selfish dispositions. In doing so, Ohaeto brings attention to our power-drunk leaders' inherent shortcomings and inconsiderate outlook. Furthermore, the poet employs satire to highlight the inhumane exploitation of their citizens by these leaders: "President dey go where e like/President dey do wetin e like/If president wan travel/Na siren dey clear road/Dem deyparamparampiroopirop/Every car go run comot for road too/Na president dey pass for road"(58). His declaration indicates that he has never witnessed a sitting president walking a considerable distance, suggesting that they are entirely extricated from the social hardships and sufferings experienced by others, thereby emphasising their detachment from the plight of the masses. The president's employees are wealthy; their wives are content, and their offspring are specially treated. The availability of special privileges, high comfort levels, and various luxuries fuel his ambition to become president, much like every other Nigerian. This is purely satirical, targeting the typical Nigerian politician who enters politics because of the prohibitive privileges it guarantees. The beauty of the language of this poem lies in its simplicity, making it accessible to every literate Nigerian.

Conclusion

Contemporary Nigerian poets exhibit a strong sense of awareness of their audience, and therefore employ a minimalist linguistic style that includes pidgin. This makes their work accessible to a wider readership. They firmly hold the view that the use of simplified language, familiar imagery, symbols, and drawing from oral traditions demonstrates a deeper commitment than styles that

may be incomprehensible to most people and intended for a select few in society. In contemporary Nigeria, many poets create poetry with simplified language to cater for the masses and the elite. The use of pidgin is an extreme form of this audience-awareness approach. However, this does not diminish its literary quality, as it is rich in literary devices that set it apart from other forms of literature. Fundamentally, this simplicity of style can facilitate social change by appealing to the audience and mobilising them to action.

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